

NOVEL APPROACH TO AQUATIC BODIES LOCOMOTION AND REVIEW OF CURRENT STATE: PART 1

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ABSTRACT

The fish locomotion has received enormous amount of attention and yet, as writing this paper, the progress is not satisfactory. On one hand, some progress is done by measuring the gravity centroid movement among other things which was done only recently. Several measurements of the velocity field around fish body also was done only recently. On the other hand, there is entrenched belief that the vortices are the source of the fish thrust. It is not mattered that this belief violates the first/second law of thermodynamics. Additionally, many of the numerical analyses contain some controversial issues.

Recently, a progress was made in the understanding of the added mass and transfer properties which provided innovative tools. This new understanding provides a fresh prospective analyzing the topic and thus, it yields new comprehension. It turned out that there are mechanisms which “hold” or restrain the fish body to the path (\mathbf{x}) while the fish “push” the liquid jet (water) back. This jet provides the fish the thrust via the enhanced transfer property for the motion and thus allowing fish a way of propelling forward. This explanation is novel approach and should be the base for future models.

NOMENCLATURE

F Force

ℓ Fish length

R_B Reynolds number

R_H Fish hydraulic radius

St St number

U fish velocity

Greek Letters

ρ density

Key Words

Transfer Properties, Gravity Centroid, Fish, Propulsion Vortices Dynamics, Added Mass, Vortices

1 Introduction

The movement of fish and other aquatic bodies can be characterized by using relatively simple fluid mechanics principles. Newton’s laws could and should explain the movements forward of simple aquatic bodies. Generally speaking, any body movement requires either pushing backward (against solid surface) or emitting/pushing material backward. Having a solid surface around, the body can apply force backward on the solid floor surface to get body propel forward. In liquid when there is no solid surfaces, the body is propelled by a liquid jet (or simply pushing liquid backward) as oppose to solid surface. This distinction is very significant for the understanding the mechanism of the fish’s propulsion¹.

It should be noted that many publications appeared in this area analyzing the aquatic body movement. These research work developments either partially violate basics fluid mechanics and thermodynamics principles or using experimental work which are predisposed for the causes. This subject can provide some understating for role the added mass and the transfer properties play. While this author does not know about reasons and motivations to study this area, the sheer fact the amount of work is a strong indication for the field importance. This area has been approached mostly (except Taylor and ?) either by biologists or CFD (numerical guys)². The results are reflection of their work.

¹One can wonder if anyone has noticed this point before.

²Reviewing this section Webb (1975) discuss the same trends. Thus, this

Literature review shows that analysis of the fish (aquatic body) with a constant velocity, at least partially, was done utilizing equation(s) which includes added mass. The added mass should appear only when there is an acceleration which can be significant. There are several other effects such enhanced transfer properties pushing forces³. Conflating various effects creates governing questions which do not describe the fish motion. If calculations of fish motions are affected by the added mass for constant velocity case, there is something fundamentally wrong with that work (Bar-Meir 2022). The controversial issues will refer to a recent single paper which is representative of this class of papers.

Current paper was initiated because the desire to study how the transfer and added mass properties are working for and during the aquatic body movements as opposed to a rigid body like ship. While the minimal understanding was gained on the transfer properties, the understanding of the fish propulsion was considerably improved and discussed here.

2 Survey of Fish Propulsion Models

Here, the focus is on a specific kind of aquatic animal (fish or even mosasaur) which has the ability to change the body shape so it can appear in a sinusoidal shape. Apparently the mechanism is different for different fish shape/category. The reason for the selection of this particular shape is to allow (or it was expected to appear) to examine the transfer properties. The principles, discussed here, can be applied to other living bodies that have the same patterns such as shark or in a jargon term: subcarangiform. While this term is used here, it should be replaced by a proper dimensionless number⁴. Perhaps the dimensionless number can be defined as ℓ/R_H (see fig. 1). Yet, while the limitations above, some concepts from this kind of fish's locomotion can be applied to the marine mammalian while recognizing the difference between rotation direction (marine mammalian are rotating in the y direction or in jargon pitch). Furthermore, some fish like a sunfish have a different character⁵ thus this analysis is not applicable for these bodies.

Fish can be considered as a tapered cylinder as a first approximation. The ratio of ℓ/R_H might be assumed to be the determine factor (ℓ/R_H) and in the range of 3.5-6. Where ℓ is the fish length and R_H here is the averaged hydraulic radius⁶. The

FIGURE 1. Schematic of sunfish to explain the ratio of the length and the hydraulic radius. The exhibit is made by redrawing on a photo “stealing” the colors and then removing the photo. The colors were extracted from this photo and two other to obtain a realistic feel

movement of fish at constant velocity in the main direction to be denoted as x . The main direction is in x and there is no added mass in this direction (no acceleration! compared to many papers which claim this added mass for constant velocity!). The fish sways in the y direction (minimally as it will be described below). Thus the added mass is active in y direction only but it is very minimal. The body experiences rotation in z direction (pointing to outside the water surface, in marine terminology yaw). Outside the water the main rotating is the parallel to water surface. For this analysis, this rotation will be ignored for two reasons: one, it seems (dimensional analysis) to be small compared to other effects and two (“more importantly”) it is hard to calculate because the rotation point is unknown.

Because the main purpose of this paper is set a new course in the discussion, the analysis of the old model will be limited (there is no need to exhibit all mistakes if no academic benefits appear.). Hence, qualitative discussion on the fish movement, so understanding of the source of movement, can be obtained.

2.1 Literature Review

There are many publications on the fish locomotion. Blake (1983) published about the fish locomotion in which he described ideal and real flow, continuity and Bernoulli equations and several other items. He even described π Buckingham theorem⁷ and boundary layer theory. Unfortunately, no real word on fish locomotion (maybe in a different version?). Lauder (2015) published a review on the current of the fish locomotion which describe two methods. The first method is referred as the resistive model initially suggested by Taylor (1952). For constant velocity, instead of calculating the thrust directly, it is estimated from the drag forces. Note, the equation was build in the pre-dimensionless era in biology (the information on the dimensional

author able was to find the distinction between propulsion in liquid and solid.

³In this paper, the transfer properties will be disguised as other elements.

⁴If you interested I can help you to developed a dimensionless number describe it properly.

⁵Dimensional analysis has not been fully worked out yet and it can to be done by someone.

⁶Representative number if the fish was squeezed to a cylinder with the same length. The radius of that cylinder is hydraulic cylinder. There might be additional factors that were not considered.

⁷Ignoring the more accurate method Nusselt/Schmidt method probably because of lack of knowledge.

FIGURE 2. Schematic of von Karman vortex street for rigid body and one for tail reorganizing the vortices. According to Tokieda and others, this rearrangement is the reason fish are moving very fast. Notice that vortices appear before actual locations not sure if the location is error or not paying attention to the details. In reality the vortex appears downstream the body. The control volume drawn around the two configurations.

analysis did not traveled fully to this research area to this day.) In this study/model, the body is divided to segments and the drag is calculated for each elements by utilizing a drag coefficient. Webb in his book (1975) citing Lighthill (1960) offered the idea of vortex shedding as the main cause of thrust. In doing so he criticized Taylor and essentially the Resistive model lost its popularity as result⁸. Webb described the history of the fish locomotion (interesting) in which he described the added mass for acceleration.

The belief, in the connection between the vortices and the propulsion, entrenched in the field. Several models/articles are selected to be mentioned which they might be important in the development of this belief. The list of researchers who worked in this area is very long. Read (2003) measured the Strouhal number for various scenarios (note that the rotation object was no similar to actual fish tail). Drucker et al (2002) took pictures to measure the velocity around the vortex. Hoppe (1989) was of the early believer in the vortex propulsion. Luznik measured the width of the wake (1998). Extensive work (Oshima and Oshima 1980) on flow visualizations pertaining to foils may be found in Scherer (1968).

Tokieda published a youtube video (Tokieda 2022) in which he describes the reorganization of von Karman vortex street. The vortex street is the unsymmetrical vortices/eddies that shed from a body as shown in left in fig. 2. Later, these vortices are consumed by the energy dissipation. The vertices are a mechanism in which energy extracted from the body to liquid and later is dissipated. There is a theoretical dispute if it occurs

⁸It is flabbergast that Taylor's idea lost the popularity as the new idea which is so weak and challenges the first and second law of thermodynamics. It just to tell you how much propaganda/CNN/ABC/NBC and alike have power.

right away. The energy for these eddies derived from the fish and hence the eddies are energy extractors (regardless to how the dissipation occurs). While Tokieda was not the one who initiate the work in this area or even conduct research, he is the one who provide a simple explanation which is easy to explain the fault of the model.

Thus, if a body (fish) moves in a constant velocity, it need continuously supply energy to compensate for the energy loss. Tokieda's claims that for rigid body the vertices are arranged not in a unfavorable field which slow down the body. Tokieda argues that when the vortices are rearranged by the tail for flexible body like (see right side fig. 2 vortices are arranged according to the tail location) the velocity field is such that a favorite arrangement occur. Tokieda points to the fact that in this arrangement, the velocity in the middle of the street, in on same direction and away from the fish as opposed to the previous case. The vortices direction is determined by the geometry and it can be thought as the wall is spinning chunks of liquid. The rotation of a vortex can be thought as if a carpet is pulled under a ball or a ball is rotating on a floor.

Tokieda's model suffers from several serious problems. The hypothesis is based on the shedding occurs at a specific timing (that is a problem). Assuming the initial conditions are ignored and the frequency was matched/synchronized somehow (there are issues with this assumption). To keep the arrangement and harmony the velocity has to be such that the vortices should be shaded at a specific location and time. Assuming that the fish has the right sensors to sense vortices and to act on it. It is well known that there is a relationship between the frequency of the shedding and the fish velocity. The following formula is applicable for the range $250 < Re < 200000$.

$$St = 0.198 \left(1 - \frac{19.7}{Re} \right) \quad (1)$$

where:

$$St = \frac{f \ell}{U} \quad (2)$$

and f is vortex shedding frequency, ℓ characteristic length of the body, and U flow velocity. This dimensionless parameter St is known as Strouhal number. The fact that this hypothesis is not supported by experiments is not the problem (Rohr and Fish 2004) and (Horton, Drucker, and Summers 2003). The frequency of the flip has to be connected **exactly** with velocity which does not occur. Yet, these (initial and upkeep) are not the real problems with this belief.

The problem is that the momentum conservation (actually Newton second law and thermodynamics second law), a princi-

ple described in great details (Bar-Meir 2021), does not support this idea. In general, the integral momentum conservation technique is accounting of the momentum in the “system” (control volume has flow in and out, and material accumulation (or reduction) in the control volume). Note that the momentum is a conserved quantity and has to be preserved in the control volume (See (Bar-Meir 2021) for more details.). The control volume around the fish and the liquid is shown in fig. 2. On both sides of the control volume, the liquid is flowing out. On the downstream border the liquid is flowing out. On the upstream border the liquid is flowing in. Comparing the two cases is done to see if the net force change due to the change in vortex location. On both sides the flow is the identical (mirror image) flow. Notice that velocity profile is taken when one vortex is crossing the boundary. Also notice that there might be a vortex in the control volume that it has zero effect on the linear momentum⁹. The change in the location of the vortex does not change net flow in at the downstream border. Hence there is no change in the upstream border. The immediate conclusion is that the two cases, as far as the acting forces concern, are the same. Furthermore, the downstream border is almost not affected by the vortex. If in both cases, the control volumes have the same velocities (momentum), and the same conditions exist e.g. the same stream out and in. Hence, the vortex does not affect the forces (resistance) on fish. Hence, this hypothesis should be rejected. Also notice that the angular momentum is a different story.

The entrenched belief that vortices are the source of the fish’s thrust can also dispel by examining the possible velocity (profile). The vertices are results of the velocity difference between the fish and the liquid (water). If there is no difference in velocities (of the fish and liquid) there are no vortices. Where the “original” vortices come from when body starts from zero velocity? Beside this theological question, the magnitude is a cardinal point. The first/second law thermodynamics requires that energy cannot come without energy input. In other word, if the body velocity is U then the combined the results of the vortices cannot be more than U . Even at that speed the velocity will not propel/accelerate the fish. The vortices are the energy lost due to the fish swimming (resistance). Hence, at best, some of this energy can be recovered by the vortices with better arrangement of the vortices. There is not enough energy in the recuperation to propel the fish but reduce the resistance.

Another idea that was floating by several papers that the water from gills add an additional thrust for the fish. Indirectly suggesting the jet propulsion by some kind pumping mechanism. There are two explanations why this explanation is not the case. The first one: the flow through the gill is continuous as opposed to the mammal breathing which is a cycle (in and out air) or the

⁹Hope that the explanation is not to short. The whole or symmetrical vortices are self canceling as linear momentum is concern.

FIGURE 3. Schematic of the mouth and the gill of a fish. Showing the cross section area of mouth is larger and the combined gill area.

jet created by squids and similar creatures which again is in a cycle. Thus, to create a jet (thrust) in a continuous manner (for a large part of the time) additional momentum (or energy) has to be supplied. The fish does not have such mechanism to add momentum or energy to the liquid (water). The second one: the control volume around gill and mouth as shown in fig. 3 exhibits one stream in and two streams out. Without exact measurement, it seems that the area in (mouth) is less than exit area (the gill cross sectional area) hence, total exit area is more than double the area for the flow in. Thus, exit velocity is about half the velocity in. In addition the flow in (mouth) is in the x direction while the exit is at angle to x . Thus, the total estimate for lost momentum is related to the fish to the square velocity $F \sim 0.75\rho\ell A_{mouth} U^2$ ¹⁰.

FIGURE 4. Schematic of the fish movements depicting how the tail is pushing the liquid. The arc shape is shown during the tail pushing.

¹⁰The logic of this analysis is straight forward and it suggested that one should read the chapter on momentum (Bar-Meir 2021). This statement is written by this author who is a thermo-fluid guy. Thus it is hard to judge if this statement is clear without over explaining.

3 The Model

There are two main mechanisms to propel boats forward: one is the oar(s) on the sides of the boat and two oar on the back which is refer to as sculling oar. The oar(s) on the side is(are) operated by pushing the oar backward (in jargon: stern). The return of the oar is done through the air and not the water. The process is not equal for back and forward. The sculling is done by having a different shape of the oar path, which is done through a movement of figure eight shape. This way, the resistance to the oar is different for different segment of the path (a better statement is the energy/momentum usage depends on the path.). This process is well known to any one who used oar to move a boat. Thus, every method has a different configurations of the operation, yet both have way to avoid the “back stroke” . The side oar does it by moving through the air medium while for the sculling oar is done by rotation of the oar.

While one can argue that these movements were copied from the fish movement to boat propulsion. Here it suggested to do the reverse and use these movements on the boat so that the fish movements can be understood. Taylor G. I. published a warning against using rigid body and yet Read (2003) use a rigid body to study flexible fish. Here, this idea is absorbed into the knowledge on how the rigid body overcome the lack of flexibility.

Examining fig. 4 shows that two interesting elements that control the fish thrust. From the physical point of view, the most efficient way for the fish to move is with zero sway (y) and a force acting in backward direction (stern). The fish structure has three mechanisms that minimize the change of the gravity centroid which include: Bernoulli effect (airfoil), added mass, the fins (anchors). Study of the movement (Loschner, Smith, and Galloway 2000) indeed demonstrates that the less these movements occur, the more efficient the movement. For a boat sculling, the change in the y direction is part of “payment” to overcome the rigidness of the oar. This difference changes the oar angle which is a bit complicate to calculate and to explain. The second mechanism is the added mass, in which increases the effective fish mass (Mass is a resistance to movement and in this case it is as fish mass or more.). The third, the fins are some kind of combination of increase of the added mass and resistive area. This airfoil shape (marked as Bernoulli in image) impose a force that object to the tail pushing (see fig. 6). This couple forces also can be observed in fig. 1 in (Müller and Van Leeuwen 2006).

Xiong et al (2014) measured the movements of gravity centroid as shown in fig. 5. This work is probably one of the most significant in the research on the fish locomotion. The reason that the gravity centroid movement in direction of y (sway) is large because thrust is result in movement in y direction. The figure shows clearly that the gravity centroid movements are synchronized with the tail movement. This is a strong experimental evidence that the thrust is not relating to vortex shedding.

The second part is the pushing backward by the tail. The

FIGURE 5. The gravity centroid in two directions. The total change in surge of order of 0.51.5 [mm], which is approximately 0.5% of body length. One the other hand, the sway movement are much more considerable and they increase with the speed. This figure is taken from Xiong and Lauder.

FIGURE 6. Schematic of a fish to demonstrate the Bernoulli (airfoil) effect and the enhance transfer property. Notice the arrow point to the forces the liquid apply to the fish body.

moving of rigid body characterized by the same angle for the entire span. The fish tail angle varies and as the radius increases the angle is such that pushing is directed backward. Hence, for the fish, the tail rotation angle can be even more than 45° and tail still point backward. Note that on the back stroke the tail is rearranged in the opposite direction (as opposed to rigid body). In this way, the tail can move in a large angle range.

While it was explained earlier in this paper, there is a point of comparison of fish to rigid body that needed to be emphasized. Denoting the tail to be zero when the tail is straight. When the head is the left and the tail is on the right, moving clockwise is positive. Consider a tail at 45° positive which is moving counter clockwise (toward the zero) in that case the tail is propelling the body. After the rigid tail is reaching to zero (straight), then when the tail continues which now hindering the body movement. This will continue until tail reaches the maximum opening. When the rigid tail returns to zero, there will be a reversal operation. There will be a cycle in which part is pushing and part is hindering (the parts are not equal, \cos vs. \sin). However, as opposed to the rigid shape, the actual fish rotation will continue pushing without the

FIGURE 7. Schematic of a rigid tail representing the fish tail. Notice the zero line marked in the figure which is the turning point for positive and negative propulsion. Once the “tail” pass the direction is reversed. Notice the velocity field is complicated and influenced by the fish velocity.

hinder. Hence, besides the optimization of the tail shape it also change shape to continue the pushing.

The explanation about this phenomena was missing from many researchers. For example, Read (2003) moved his “toy” in a linear action while the toy supposed to be rotating. The predisposed conception is a typical approach in this field. It is a shiny object when one see his own limitations. Lauder noted that it is active research and his words “[s]urprisingly little is known about COM motion during undulatory.” The strange jargon COM refers to center of mass (strange notation, One can guess that every field like to invent their jargon or not aware that it is called gravity centroid.).

4 Review of Numerical Work

Many numerical works in the area are such that can be described as a fictional work. This author is not aware of a single work that can be qualified as a good both from the writing or logic and knowledge of the physics of swimming such as added mass, transfer properties¹¹. Yet, the numerical techniques them self did improved significantly. The fact that one used powerful tools does not make the model correct or reasonable. An excellent demonstration of such case is the critical velocity in die casting. A die casting a manufacturing process in which a liquid metal is injected and forced into a mold and cooled very rapidly. To prevent the porosity (one of the reasons), the plunger has to

¹¹Some of the latest papers are so poorly written when compared to Froude (?) writing is astonishing. One expect the English to improve with time, yet many papers are simply gibberish. It is not refers to spelling and grammar but to logic to statements without any meaning etc.

move in a critical (specific) velocity. Over last 30 (198x-2021) years with over 300 different teams attempted to solve the problem (of course, all claim that they solved the problem and they “have” the experimental evidence to “prove” it. Only question why so many teams had to repeat the same research?). They did not solve the problem because lack of understanding of the physics/fluid mechanics (Bar-Meir and Brauner 2021).

The new understanding of such things like the added mass are essential in the understating of aquatic locomotion. The added mass should show up in the analysis for accelerated aquatic bodies. For example, in (Paniccia, Graziani, Lugni, and Piva 2022) momentum equation(s) (3.15) the added mass appears even though there is no acceleration in large sections (One can only wonder how the added mass is defined for this paper.). In the definition of the added momentum of inertia due to rotation but the rotation point is not defined. The moment of inertia depends on the rotation point according the definition of the moment of inertia. In some cases, it is reasonable to assume that the rotation point is at the gravity centroid especially when the body is rotating in vacuum. Unfortunately, the fish in not in vacuum and the rotation point is unknown and depends on geometry of the fins and such. In the said paper is like the many of the solutions for critical velocity in die casting. For example, the fish for the linear motion, has only a sole added mass. Yet, equation (3.15) is not affected by the acceleration (may be a mistake). Actually it is fundamental point, the matrix creates situations in which there is no added mass effect and yet it is used in the equation(s). Furthermore, the transfer properties are conflated with the added mass.

Additionally, the introduction of the transfer properties clarifies the physics at hand. The differences between the added mass and transfer properties (which commonly conflated) are that the added mass appears only when the body accelerated while transfer properties appear when the body or the surroundings are on the move (relatively). The added mass depends on the acceleration direction and the transfer properties depend on the relative direction of velocity (of the liquid or/and the body). Please note said paper is a representative and acts as a summary of many papers and concepts presented in the paper are from many other researchers. There are several assumption that are controversial such as the momentum is fix in the control volume of the fish plus the liquid. This conservation should read momentum is conserved for the fish and liquid and forces that acting on boundaries. While the velocities are vanished at the boundaries, the integration of the forces on the boundaries is not.

5 Results and Discussion

Several points were made here in regard the old models and current state in fish propulsion understanding. It was shown that the rearrangement of von Karman vortex street at maximally reduce the fish resistance but it does not propel the aquatic creature. It

was shown that possibly mechanisms that based on the physics are actually explain how the fish propels itself.

Concluding Remarks

Obviously this paper is different from all the papers published earlier in this area because the paper proposed totally new idea(s) and alleged that old model, at least in part, violates the second law of thermodynamics. Thus if you believe that the ideas in this paper are correct, it should change the way you deals with fish propulsion. If you do not believe in these idea, you are welcome to criticize the paper, all remarks on paper/email are appreciated. This section is the first part of the install. Currently, the second part is a draft form and may or may not published.

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